

Patient-specific quality assurance in SBRT treatments using 3D polymer gel dosimetry

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ABSTRACT

In stereotactic body radiation therapy (SBRT), patient-specific quality assurance (PSQA) is required due to the complex dose distributions delivered. In this context, polymer gels are considered reliable as a three-dimensional dosimeter. This work used polymer MAGIC-gel sealed in 2 mm thin-wall glass spheres to assess the three-dimensional (3D) dose distribution imparted to patients and compared the results with that provided by the treatment planning system. Four SBRT treatments targeting vertebral, ilium, pelvic lymph node and lung regions were selected for this study. A computed tomography (CT) scan of each glass sphere was obtained, and the patient treatment plan was superimposed on the glass sphere CT image. Thereafter, the spheres were irradiated under similar conditions to the patient using a Varian TrueBeam linear accelerator. A high-spatial resolution optical CT scanner was used to read the glass sphere containing the gel. Planned and delivered 3D dose distributions were compared quantitatively through 3D gamma passing rates at several selected acceptance criteria and qualitatively through the evaluation of dose-profiles, isodose-curves, and dose-volume histograms. We observed that the overall 3D gamma passing rate exceeded 90% at acceptance criteria of 2% dose difference and 2 mm distance-to-agreement for a dose threshold of 20%. The results of this study suggest that the polymer MAGIC-gel sealed in thin-wall glass spheres in conjunction with the optical CT readout method is a suitable PSQA system for SBRT treatments.

1. Introduction

Stereotactic body radiation therapy (SBRT) is an advanced radiotherapy technique able to deliver high radiation doses to the target volume, while protecting surrounding normal tissues. Characterized by a single or few fractions, SBRT requires radiation field modulation through multileaf collimators to ensure the radiation beam conformation (Xia et al. 2020). Given the complexity of the dose distribution delivered, a rigorous patient-specific quality assurance (PSQA) framework is essential for the successful implementation of these treatments (Xia et al. 2020).

For treatment plan verification, standard dosimeters like ionization chambers, diodes, thermoluminescent dosimeters (TLDs) and films are predominantly used (Baldock et al. 2010). Nevertheless, these methods are limited due to their incapacity to provide three-dimensional information since they can only measure at a point or on a plane. Recently, a new generation of high-resolution 2D detector arrays, such as MyQA®

SRS, Matrixx Resolution, ArcCHECK and SRS MapCHECK and Varian aS1200 electronic portal imaging device (EPID) is becoming commercially available and has been used as SBRT and SRS QA devices (Padelli et al. 2022; James et al. 2023). Despite the availability of these electronic 2D detector arrays, challenges persist since they lack sufficient spatial resolution (Ahmed et al. 2019) or due to the expensive costs.

The integration of polymer gels coupled with imaging techniques for 3D dose mapping offers a possible solution to overcome these issues. Polymer gel dosimeters change their structure when exposed to ionizing radiation. This is caused by the interaction of radicals produced by water radiolysis with embedded monomers, initiating a polymerization process. The resulting polymer chains, proportional to the incident radiation, become enclosed within the gelatin matrix, encoding spatial information about the dose distribution (Su, 2013). These structural changes impact the gel's mechanical, optical, and magnetic properties, allowing the use of techniques like magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) (Papagiannis et al. 2005; Fernandes et al., 2010; Jaszczak et al. 2018),

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Table 1
Mass percentage for individual compounds in the MAGIC gel formulation.

Compound	Mass percentage (%)
Ultra-pure Milli-Q water	65.8
Glucose	14.9
Gelatin (300 bloom, type A)	8.0
Methacrylic acid	6.0
Urea	4.7
Hydroquinone	0.6
Ascorbic acid	0.0352
Copper Sulfate	0.00075

optical computed tomography (OCT) (Maryanski et al. 1994; Awad et al. 2019; Rousseau et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2003), and X-ray computed tomography (Hilts et al. 2000; Jirasek et al., 2010; Jirasek and Hilts, 2009) for readout.

In MRI, the measurement is based on spin-spin relaxation rate R2 (Pappas et al., 1999). In the OCT case, changes in optical density, which is the fraction of light absorbed by a material, could be related to the absorbed dose through a calibration process (Oldham et al. 2001).

So far, several gel formulations coupled with different imaging techniques have been used to investigate the performance of 3D gel dosimetry in external radiotherapy beams (Vanossi et al. 2010, da Silveira et al. 2014, De Deene et al. 2015; Høye et al. 2015; Rousseau et al. 2022, Magugliani et al., 2023, Awad et al. 2019, Colnot et al. 2022, Al Kafi et al. 2021, Papagiannis et al. 2005, etc.). However, only few studies have been concentrated on the use of 3D gel dosimetry for performing PSQA in radiotherapy (Awad et al. 2019; Colnot et al. 2022; Al Kafi et al. 2021; da Silveira et al., 2014; Papagiannis et al. 2005). Al Kafi and colleagues used CrystalBalls (MGS Research Inc.) filled with tissue-equivalent radiochromic polymer gel dosimeter associated with an OCT scanner to assess the 3D dose distribution delivered to patients diagnosed with brain metastasis, trigeminal neuralgia, spine metastasis, prostate cancer, lung cancer and liver cancer during CyberKnife robotic radiotherapy treatments. To quantitatively compare with the dose distribution delivered by the treatment planning system (TPS), they evaluated the 3D gamma index finding a passing rate of $(90.5 \pm 6.7) \%$ at acceptance criteria of 2%/2 mm for a dose threshold of 20% (Awad et al. 2019; Al Kafi et al. 2021). Colnot and colleagues used a patient-based 3D printed phantom for personalized PSQA filled with liquid water and a gel jar to investigate the 3D dose distribution received by a patient with a right mesencephalic brain tumour. They reported a 3D gamma passing rate of 96.3% at acceptance criteria of 2%/1 mm estimated within the central 85% of the jar volume (Colnot et al. 2022). However, it is not clear what was the percentage dose threshold used. In a previous work, da Silveira and co-workers (da Silveira et al. 2014) used MAGIC-f gel coupled with MRI technique to determine the 3D dose distribution delivered during two prostate intensity-modulated radiation therapy (IMRT) treatment plans. They compared the dose images from the gel with the treatment planning images finding a gamma index passing rate

of 95.5% and 94.0% at acceptance criteria of 3%/3 mm for both treatment plans without any dose threshold.

This work used polymer MAGIC gel associated with an OCT to determine the 3D dose distribution of four SBRT treatments targeting vertebral, ilium, pelvic lymph node and lung regions and compare with that provided by the TPS. This approach served to conduct PSQA tests for 4 patients. MAGIC gel was chosen due to its normoxic nature, allowing an easy production in the presence of oxygen. In this type of gel, the response is attributed to the polymerization of methacrylic acid, and protection against oxygen interference is achieved through the formation of a copper ascorbic acid complex (Fong et al. 2001). The original MAGIC gel was modified to increase the dose sensitivity by adding glucose and urea (Zhu et al. 2010).

2. Materials and methods

The characteristics of the planning target volumes (PTV) studied are the following: (a) Vertebral (PTV 14 Gy, volume (V) = 17.3 cm³, equivalent sphere diameter (D) = 3.2 cm; integrated boost PTV 20 Gy: V = 1.5 cm³, D = 1.4 cm); b) Lung (PTV 30 Gy, V = 1.6 cm³, D = 1.4 cm); c) Ilium (PTV 21 Gy, V = 20.9 cm³, D = 3.4 cm); d) Pelvic lymph node (PTV 24 Gy, V = 10.2 cm³, D = 2.7 cm).

2.1. Gel manufacturing

The chemical composition of the MAGIC gel expressed as a mass percentage is displayed in Table 1. The preparation process follows the steps described previously by Zhu and colleagues (Zhu et al., 2010). First, fresh solutions of copper sulfate (0.0005 g/ml) and ascorbic acid (0.0176 g/ml) were prepared using a fraction of the total water volume and then set aside. Glucose and urea were added to water at room temperature and mixed. Once dissolved, type A gelatin (300 Bloom, Sigma-Aldrich®) was incorporated and heated to 48 °C. The mixture was maintained at this temperature until the gelatin completely melted, then hydroquinone was introduced. Subsequently, the heater was turned off, and the mixture was cooled down to 37 °C. Ascorbic acid (Meyer®) and copper sulfate (Meyer®) solutions were then added, for each 50 g of gel, 0.75 ml of copper sulfate and 1 ml of ascorbic acid were incorporated. After approximately 5 min, methacrylic acid (Sigma®) was finally introduced. The solution was continuously stirred throughout the entire mixing process. The gel was then poured into five 2 mm thickness glass sphere flask phantoms, each with a diameter of 16.2 cm.

It has been reported that a gel sample is a representative of an entire batch (Cardenas et al. 2002; Magugliani et al. 2023); therefore, in this work one of the flasks was used for batch calibration and the remaining four were allocated for treatment verification. The flasks were sealed with rubber caps and paraffin film, and then stored in a refrigerator at a temperature of about 4 °C for a minimum of 24 h before irradiation to guarantee the crosslinking reaction in the gelatin matrix of the gel phantom. Due to the low melting point of the MAGIC-gel, all the flasks

Fig. 1. (a) Calibration plan setup in the TPS (axial plane, 10 cm depth from the beam entrance in the water phantom). (b) Alignment with lasers for calibration. (c) Post-irradiation image of the phantom, showing the gel opacity changes in field-impacted regions.

Fig. 2. Dose distribution resulting from exporting the vertebral SBRT plan from the patient's CT (a) to the gel CT (b).

were continuously conserved in the refrigerator after each process.

2.2. Treatment planning and gel irradiation

A single gel phantom was used for the calibration. In this case, the setup involved several $3 \times 3 \text{ cm}^2$ fields in the axial plane of the gel phantom, irradiated with doses from 1 Gy to 50 Gy at 10 cm depth within the gel (Fig. 1a) at a dose rate of 600 UM/min. The contribution to the dose due to scattered radiation produced by the proximity of the beams was taken into account by applying an iterative process of the monitor units required to deliver the specified dose at the reference points of each field within the gel phantom. During the irradiation, the glass sphere was immersed in a liquid water phantom (Fig. 1b and c), to simulate the reference dose measurements during the linac calibration using an ionization chamber (IAEA TRS 398, 2000; Andreo et al. 2020; IAEA TRS 483, 2017).

The combined standard uncertainties in the calibration curve include the uncertainty from the dose rates (2%, $k=1$) and from the TPS, whereas the uncertainty in the optical density per cm includes the standard deviation of the ROI averaged over four slices of 0.1 mm thickness.

We investigated four SBRT treatment plans targeting vertebral, ilium, pelvic lymph node, and lung regions, created with the Varian Eclipse TPS v.16.1 at the radiation therapy Department of the hospital. Such treatment plans were previously verified under the hospital's protocol before delivering to the corresponding patients. That protocol consists in assessing a central slice of the treatment plan using EBT-XD radiochromic film. The film was positioned at a source-to-surface distance of 100 cm between two 5 cm thick acrylic phantom. A 2D gamma evaluation is performed by comparing the measurements with the film to the calculation performed by the TPS on the equivalent slice after exporting the treatment plan to the computed tomography of the acrylic phantom.

To simulate the conditions of the patients, the plans were exported to

Fig. 3. Laser OCTOPUS-RR OCT scanner where the different parts can be seen.

the gel phantom's geometry using an acquired computed tomography (CT) phantom image (Fig. 2). The dose-to-water (Yan et al. 2017) distribution for all the treatment plans was calculated using the Anisotropic Analytical Algorithm (AAA) version 1610 by choosing a grid size of 1.25 mm. The calculated dose distribution in the TPS for the phantom was exported as an RTDose DICOM file for comparison. Thereafter, the gel phantoms were irradiated under similar conditions of the patients using a 6 MV FFF X-ray beam generated by a Varian TrueBeam SN 1717 linear accelerator (linac) with a dose rate of 1200 MU/min. All the irradiation consists of a single fraction with a total dose between 20 and 30 Gy in the planning target volume (PTV). All the gel phantoms were irradiated one week post fabrication at most.

Fig. 4. Changes in the opacity of the gel phantom for the calibration and the SBRT treatment plan measurements: (a, b) calibration; (c) vertebral, (d) lung, (e) ilium and (f) pelvic lymph node.

2.3. Gel image acquisition and reconstruction process

The reading process was carried out using a commercial laser OCT scanner OCTOPUS-RR manufactured by MGS Research Inc. (see Fig. 3). This scanner uses a 5 mW, 635 nm polarized laser pencil beam (Al Kafi et al. 2021). One or two days after the fabrication of the gel, an initial scan of the phantoms was performed and 24h after, the irradiation was made. To ensure the polymerization reaction stabilization, all the irradiated gel phantoms were read at least 24 h post-irradiation. For all readings, the gel phantoms were submerged in the OCT immersion liquid to achieve optical coupling of the flask with its surroundings. During the reading process, 3D-printed supports were used to embrace the neck of the flask and secure the phantom's rotation on the z-axis. The starting position of the laser was always fixed below the upper level of the gel in the flask. To ensure reproducibility of the flask's orientation in the OCT, the CT scan and the linac, a mark was made on the 3D-printed supports and the neck of the flask so they can always be aligned with each other. The software Octopus-RR laser CT DAQ, R2019b was used to acquire the images. For the acquisition process, the scanner allows 400 projections per revolution, equivalent to one projection every 0.9° .

The acquisition parameters in the OCT were consistent for all images: 250 slices, 0.5 mm slice thickness resulting in an effective height of 12.5 cm for the 3D dose distribution measurement. The acquisition time per slice was approximately 15 s. For the reconstruction, we used the LCT-OCTOPUS software provided by the manufacturer (MGS Research Inc.). This software used filtered back projection with the Shepp-Logan filter (Gore et al. 1996; Xu et al. 2004) to reconstruct the optical density per cm (OD/cm) in each slice (Al Kafi et al. 2021) with a pixel resolution of $0.5 \times 0.5 \text{ mm}^2$. The noise in the image was previously evaluated and found to be in the order of 3.5×10^{-4} OD/cm. Finally, the obtained images were stored in TIFF format and post-processed using Python and Matlab® software for subsequent analysis. Total variation algorithm

was implemented though Chambolle-Pock algorithm (weight = 2), to reduce noise in all images. The images of the gel phantom for the treatment plans were transformed into 3D absorbed dose distribution using the calibration curve.

2.4. Dose distribution comparison

The comparison between dose distributions measured with the gel and those calculated from the Treatment Planning System (TPS) was carried out using gamma analysis (Low and Dempsey, 2003). This analysis was performed using a library in Python for medical physics called PyMedPhys (Biggs et al., 2022). We evaluated the global gamma passing rates for the clinical tolerance criteria of 3% dose variation and 3 mm distance-to-agreement (DTA) as well as stricter criteria, including 2.5%/2.5 mm and 2%/2 mm, using a dose threshold of 20% which is commonly used in practice (da Silveira et al. 2014; Al Kafi et al. 2021). The test was considered successful if the gamma index was smaller than 1 for at least 90% of the pixels evaluated. Additionally, the dose profiles, isodose curves, dose difference maps, and dose-volume histograms (DVH) of both dose distributions were qualitatively compared. For the DVH, rigid registration of patients and phantom CT scans were performed. Subsequently, the structures of interest in the patient's CT were exported to the gel phantom to calculate the dose under such conditions. The calculated dose was then compared with the measured dose in the phantom for the same exported structures.

3. Results and discussions

Fig. 4a and b displays the gel phantom after exposure to several beams for calibration purposes, while Fig. 4c-f presents those exposed to the four SBRT treatment plans. From all figures, changes in the gels due to ionizing radiation exposure are evident. From Fig. 4c-f, the opaque

Fig. 5. Dose response for MAGIC-f gel exhibiting a second-degree polynomial relationship within the measured dose range.

portions embedded in the gel show the contribution of the different modulated beams of the SBRT treatment plans. In the phantom irradiated for calibration, only five fields with delivered doses ≥ 5 Gy were detectable by the OCT. The MAGIC gel calibration curve shown in Fig. 5 exhibits a polynomial behavior represented by the following equation: Dose (Gy) = $a + b$ (OD/cm) + c (OD/cm)² where $a = 0$, $b = -12.34 \pm 14.53$, $c = 419.67 \pm 44.63$ with $R^2 = 0.9976$.

The calibration curve shows a non-linear behavior, which deviates from the linear response interval of optical density (OD) versus dose reported in some other works (Massillon-JL et al., 2010; Vanossi et al. 2010; Xu et al. 2010), but none of these studies involved the MAGIC gel. Another study (Watanabe et al. 2017) mentioned that a second-degree

polynomial is the most common response for 3D dosimeters. Therefore, we considered fitting the curve with a second-degree polynomial, since the experimental data are better described mainly at doses smaller than 10 Gy, where the proportionality observed at greater doses breaks down.

Previous studies where magnetic resonance imaging is used as the readout system, the MAGIC gel commonly shows sensitivity to doses as low as 1 Gy (Zhu et al. 2010, Fernandes et al., 2010). Nonetheless, with the OCT scanner, we cannot measure the gel response below 5 Gy. The very low sensitivity observed in the gel-OCT reading system at doses < 10 Gy could be attributed to the high dispersion and attenuation of the laser beam caused by the dense structures created by the highest dose regions within the gel phantom and/or a limitation of the OCT scanner itself caused by an inadequate wavelength. One possible solution to overcome this limitation is to make individual calibration instead of using several fields within a single gel phantom or the use of accumulative dose method (Massillon-JL et al., 2010), or the use of a different wavelength.

The 3D dose distributions measured for all the SBRT treatment plans match closely those obtained from the TPS. Fig. 6 shows different slices in the x-y plane of the calculated and measured dose distribution for vertebral SBRT treatment, corresponding to a region of the object evaluated at $7 \times 7 \times 7$ cm³ (1.25 mm pixel size, 56 pixels per side and 175616 pixels per image). Isodose curves for two different planes and horizontal dose profiles are depicted in Fig. 7, all demonstrating a reasonable agreement, facilitating a qualitative assessment of the concordance between the TPS and the measurements.

Table 2 presents the results of the 3D gamma index test at different acceptance criteria for the four SBRT treatments studied using MAGIC-gel. For comparison, the 2D gamma index for the same SBRT treatments using EBT-XD radiochromic film is displayed in Table 3. Note the high average passing rates greater than 98% obtained with the film versus the gel. However, it is important to highlight that the gamma index from the film is the result of only one slice, which is not necessarily representative of the entire treatment volume.

It is evident from Table 2 that for the conventional acceptance

Fig. 6. Comparison between the dose distributions in Gy for nine selected slices from the vertebral treatment. The left panel displayed the calculated dose while the right panel the measured one.

Fig. 7. (a): Two slices illustrating the dose distributions (DD) for qualitative comparison; (b) Overlay of isodose curves from both dose distributions where the numbers represent the absorbed dose in Gy; (c): assessment of horizontal dose profiles.

criterion for volumetric modulated arc therapy (VMAT) of 3%/3 mm, the gamma passing rate exceeds 98%, while for the criterion of 2%/2 mm considered as the minimum acceptable for SRS/SBRT (Miften et al. 2018) it surpasses 90%. As mentioned in the introduction, Al Kafi and colleagues (Al Kafi et al. 2021) investigated twelve CyberKnife robotic radiotherapy and radiosurgery treatment plans using a commercial 3D PSQA system integrated by tissue-equivalent radiochromic polymer gel dosimeters sealed in light protective thin-wall glass spheres (Crystal-Balls) associated with a software (VOLQA) for scan registration and data

analysis. They used an OCT scanner similar to ours. The 3D gamma passing rates averaged over the twelve patients reported in their work agree reasonably well with those obtained in our work. For example at 20% dose threshold, they found averaged 3D gamma passing rates of $(96.0 \pm 3.1) \%$ and $(90.5 \pm 6.7) \%$ at acceptance criteria of 3%/3 mm and 2%/2 mm, respectively (Al Kafi et al. 2021). In our study, averaged passing rates of $(98.4 \pm 0.7) \%$ and $(90.6 \pm 0.8) \%$ at 3%/3 mm and 2%/2 mm, respectively were obtained for the same cutoff dose despite the difference in the 3D PSQA system used.

Table 2
3D Gamma passing rates for all the treatments by gel dosimetry.

Gamma criteria		SBRT treatment				Average
Dose difference (%)	Distance-to-agreement (mm)	Vertebral	Ilium	Pelvic lymph node	Lung	
3.0	3.0	98.72	98.81	98.82	97.32	98.4 ± 0.7
3.0	2.5	95.46	97.53	96.76	95.26	96.3 ± 1.1
3.0	2.0	91.46	96.44	92.07	92.93	93.2 ± 2.2
2.5	3.0	98.55	97.32	98.14	97.06	97.8 ± 0.7
2.5	2.5	95.13	96.58	93.33	93.75	94.7 ± 1.5
2.5	2.0	91.16	95.28	91.59	91.15	92.3 ± 2.0
2.0	3.0	98.37	96.15	97.75	96.12	97.1 ± 1.1
2.0	2.5	94.76	94.32	91.19	91.19	92.9 ± 1.9
2.0	2.0	90.04	91.80	90.22	90.13	90.6 ± 0.8

Table 3
2D Gamma passing rates for all the treatments by radiochromic film dosimetry.

Gamma criteria		SBRT treatment				Average
Dose difference (%)	Distance-to-agreement (mm)	Vertebral	Ilium	Pelvic lymph node	Lung	
3	3	98.62	100	100	100	99.7 ± 0.6
3	2.5	97.59	100	100	100	99.4 ± 1.0
3	2	95.73	99.99	100	100	98.9 ± 1.9
2.5	3	98.44	100	100	100	99.6 ± 0.7
2.5	2.5	97.25	100	100	100	99.3 ± 1.2
2.5	2	95.09	99.94	100	100	98.8 ± 2.1
2	3	98.2	100	100	100	99.6 ± 0.8
2	2.5	96.76	100	100	100	99.2 ± 1.4
2	2	94.04	99.93	99.99	99.99	98.5 ± 2.6

The gamma index test results in our work are reasonable, demonstrating a level of agreement for a 3D comparison with a considerable number of evaluated points. These outcomes suggest the potential success of the MAGIC gel-OCT system for PSQA of SBRT treatments. However, discrepancies observed in the presented results are presumably attributed to inaccuracies in the positioning of the dose distribution image from the OCT relative to that from the CT and/or to the low sensitivity of the MAGIC-gel to doses smaller than 10 Gy.

From Table 2, note that the 3D gamma passing rate is more sensitive to changes in DTA than to dose differences. This observation agrees with results reported previously (Magugliani et al. 2023). Therefore, uncertainties associated with the positioning of one dose distribution relative to another, like initial slice selection or trimming of the TPS dose distribution, represented a significant source of uncertainty for the comparison. This is important, especially in regions with high dose gradients where alignment in one direction does not guarantee correspondence in another due to possible rotations. To address these issues, it would be beneficial to implement a software for achieving optimal positioning between dose distributions iteratively, as done in the work

reported by Al Kafi and colleagues (Al Kafi et al. 2021). In their work, they used a software to facilitate workflow autocalibration, analysis and registration of both images. This can significantly reduce the time required for these three-dimensional analyses and improve reproducibility.

Fig. 8 displays for the vertebral treatment a map of the dose difference between both dose distributions (bottom left) and another of the spatial distribution for the gamma index of 2%/2 mm (bottom right). In the latter, points with values greater than one and failing the test are highlighted in red. Fig. 9 presents the differential dose-volume histogram (DVH) for the same treatment.

In the DVHs, apparent agreement in the shape of the histograms for both the measured and TPS-calculated data is observed. Nevertheless, a displacement between the curves is visible, suggesting that the overlapping of anatomic structures from the CT and the dose distribution within the gel phantom might generate histograms that are highly sensitive to the registration of the images. In these histograms, the inclusion or exclusion of certain voxels, even with millimetric shifts in any direction, can cause shifts in the DVH. This phenomenon can also be attributed to the high dose gradients generated at the boundaries of the structure during the planning process. Additionally, it cannot be guaranteed that, following image registration, the alignment of the structure with respect to the dose distribution is exact. Therefore, like the dose profiles and isodose curves, uncertainties in positioning can possibly influence these results.

4. Conclusions

Although gel dosimetry is not a conventional methodology for quality assurance in radiotherapy, its application in this study allowed for a three-dimensional comparison of dose distributions delivered during SBRT treatments. The results obtained for the gamma index test seem satisfactory, especially for 3%/3 mm, and even for more restrictive criteria (2%/2 mm). The methodology used in this study can be improved: optimizing the gel's sensitivity for doses under 10 Gy is imperative enhancing the thermal stability of the gel and optimizing procedures for manufacturing, reading, calibration, and results analysis. The inclusion of an automatic optimization method for positioning one dose distribution relative to another before the gamma analysis should be beneficial. Thus, this work supports the implementation of PSQA tests using MAGIC gel dosimeters combined with OCT for advanced radiotherapy techniques, highlighting the advantage of assessing three-dimensional dose distribution with high spatial resolution of an entire treatment volume.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

P.J. Guadarrama-Huerta: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **E. Arzaga-Barajas:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **A. Rodríguez-Laguna:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **J.A. Jiménez-Acosta:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation. **M.A. Poitevin-Chacón:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Investigation, Conceptualization. **G. Massillon-JI:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Fig. 8. Dose distributions in the x-y plane from the vertebral treatment obtained with gel (top left) and provided by the TPS (top right), with their 2D dose difference map (bottom left) and gamma index spatial distribution (bottom right).

Fig. 9. Differential (left) and cumulative (right) dose volume histograms for the vertebral integrated boost SBRT treatment.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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